

Figure 9b: 33x33 vāstu, MY 4 y+2-y+5 and MY comm 4 y+2-y+5

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|----------------|--------------|---------------|--------------------|
| 1 Brahmā | 17 Mahendra | 33 Puṣpadanta | |
| 2 Marīci | 18 Sūrya | 34 Pracetas | 49 Pilipiccha/ṁcha |
| 3 Vivasvant | 19 Satya | 35 Asura | 50 Carakī |
| 4 Mitra | 20 Bhṛśa | 36 Śoṣa | 51 Vidārī |
| 5 Pṛthivīdhara | 21 Antarikṣa | 37 Roga | 52 Pūtanā |
| 6 Āpa | 22 Agni | 38 Vāyu | 53 Pāparākṣasī |
| 7 Āpavatsa | 23 Pūṣan | 39 Nāga | |
| 8 Savitr̥ | 24 Vitatha | 40 Mukhya | |
| 9 Sāvitrī | 25 Gṛhakṣata | 41 Bhallāṭa | |
| 10 Indra | 26 Yama | 42 Soma | |
| 11 Indrajaya | 27 Gandharva | 43 Ṛgi | |
| 12 Rudra | 28 Bhṛṅga | 44 Aditi | |
| 13 Rudrajaya | 29 Mṛga | 45 Diti | |
| 14 Īśa | 30 Piṭṛ | 46 Skanda | |
| 15 Parjanya | 31 Dauvārika | 47 Aryaman | |
| 16 Jaya | 32 Sugrīva | 48 Jambhaka | |

53			49				50		
	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	14
	37	13		5			6		15
	36	12					7		16
	35								17
48	34	4		1			2		18
	33								19
	32	11					8		20
	31	12		3			9		21
	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22
52			47				51		